

Abstract**Assessment of Mother-To-Child Transmission of HIV, Maternal ART Coverage, and Early Infant Diagnosis Outcomes in Bauchi State, Nigeria**

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Background: Ending mother-to-child transmission (MTCT) of HIV remains pivotal to achieving epidemic control. Nigeria's progress depends on ensuring that every pregnant woman living with HIV receives sustained ART and that all HIV-exposed infants are promptly tested and treated. This study assessed Bauchi State's 2024 prevention of mother-to-child transmission (PMTCT) cascade and progress toward elimination of mother-to-child transmission of HIV in Bauchi State by assessing maternal ART coverage and early infant diagnosis performance.

Methods: Routine PMTCT data uploaded to the national data reporting system were analysed. Indicators included HIV testing coverage, ART status, infant prophylaxis, and early infant diagnosis (EID).

Results: Among 429,559 ANC clients, 341,479 (79.5%) were tested for HIV, with 45 (0.013%) newly positive and 279 (0.08%) previously known, giving 324 HIV-positive pregnant women. Of these, 280 (86.4%) were already on ART, and 41 (12.7%) initiated treatment during ANC. Facility deliveries totalled 23,590, including 197 (0.84%) HIV-positive mothers with 122 live births. However, 296 HIV-exposed infants received ARV prophylaxis, 271 (91%) within 72 hours and 25 (8%) after. This higher infant count likely includes births outside reporting facilities linked retrospectively. Only 78 (26%) infants had DNA-PCR testing within 72 hours, 123 (41%) within two months, and three (12%) of 25 results received were HIV-positive.

Conclusion: Bauchi State achieved high maternal HIV testing and ART coverage but showed significant gaps in early infant diagnosis and data harmonisation across service points. Strengthening delivery tracking, rapid sample transport, and timely EID feedback will consolidate PMTCT gains and accelerate progress toward elimination of mother-to-child transmission targets.

Keywords: PMTCT, HIV, Maternal ART, Early Infant Diagnosis, Bauchi State, Nigeria

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